

RESEARCH ARTICLE

RESEARCH ON SIMILARITY MATCHING OF DAZU ROCK CARVINGS IN CHINA BASED ON A TRIMODAL FUSION OF PHASH, SIFT, AND MSROVGG

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Figure 1. Filial Piety Sutra transformation.

ABSTRACT. Song Dynasty grottoes, represented by the Dazu Rock Carvings, exhibit pronounced artistic standardization and stylistic convergence. However, conventional similarity assessments of cultural relics remain heavily reliant on qualitative expert experience, which often results in inconsistent evaluations and lacks the quantitative rigor necessary for refined digital conservation and restoration. To address this, we propose a quantitative evaluation model based on trimodal feature fusion. The framework first employs the Perceptual Hash (pHash) algorithm for global structural

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screening of orthophotos, followed by the integration of the SIFT operator to extract high-dimensional texture features and perform local keypoint matching. Finally, an improved MSRoVGG deep learning architecture is incorporated to achieve deep feature verification at the semantic level. Using the Seven Buddhas of the Present Kalpa in the Dazu Rock Carvings as a case study, the results demonstrate a 100% recognition rate for identical statue types within the same niche. Furthermore, the model successfully discriminates between different iconographic types, effectively capturing semantic variations in artistic styles and vestimentary features between Buddhist and secular figures. These findings confirm the model's robust capability in typological classification and stylistic differentiation.

KEYWORDS. *Dazu Rock Carvings, China, Similarity Matching, pHash, SIFT, MSRoVGG, Trimodal Fusion.*

RESUMEN. *Las grutas de la Dinastía Song, representadas por las esculturas rupestres de Dazu, presentan una marcada estandarización artística y convergencia estilística. Sin embargo, las evaluaciones convencionales de similitud de reliquias culturales siguen dependiendo en gran medida de la experiencia cualitativa de expertos, lo cual suele dar lugar a evaluaciones inconsistentes y carece del rigor cuantitativo necesario para una conservación y restauración digital refinada. Para solucionarlo, proponemos un modelo de evaluación cuantitativa basado en la fusión de características trimodales. El marco utiliza primero el algoritmo perceptual Hash (pHash) para el cribado estructural global de ortofotos; a continuación, integra el operador SIFT para extraer características de textura de alta dimensión y realizar el emparejamiento de puntos clave locales. Finalmente, se incorpora una arquitectura de aprendizaje profundo MSRoVGG mejorada para lograr la verificación de características profundas a nivel semántico. Utilizando como caso de estudio los Siete Budas del Kalpa Presente en las esculturas rupestres de Dazu, los resultados muestran una tasa de reconocimiento del 100% para tipos de estatuas idénticos dentro del mismo nicho. Además, el modelo distingue con éxito entre diferentes tipos iconográficos, capturando eficazmente las variaciones semánticas en el estilo artístico y los rasgos indumentarios entre figuras budistas y seculares. Estos resultados confirman la solidez del modelo en la clasificación tipológica y la diferenciación estilística.*

PALABRAS CLAVE. *Esculturas rupestres de Dazu, China, emparejamiento de similitud, pHash, SIFT, MSRoVGG, fusión trimodal.*

1. INTRODUCTION

The Dazu Rock Carvings, located in Dazu District, Chongqing, China, represent the pinnacle of Chinese grotto art from the 9th to the 13th centuries (Zhou 2025). Comprising over 75,000 statues across 75 protected sites, it is a UNESCO World Heritage Site and is widely regarded as one of the Four Great Grottoes of China, alongside Dunhuang, Longmen, and Yungang (Li *et al.* 2025).

The carvings are celebrated for their grand scale, exquisite craftsmanship, and the profound integration of Buddhist, Taoist, and Confucian ideologies (Hong 2024; Zhou 2025). Specifically, Cave 15 of the Baoding Mountain site, known as the Tableaux of the Sutra on the Profound Kindness of Parents, stands as a masterpiece of secularized Buddhist art. Within this grand narrative composition, there are numerous figures of parents and children carved with strikingly similar aesthetic features, portraying the ten stages of child-rearing (Figure 1). These almost identical facial expressions and fluid drapery patterns reflect the standardized Dazu

style developed by the Zhao family of stone-carving masters during the Southern Song Dynasty.

Determining the stylistic affinities between these statues is pivotal for deciphering the artistic lineages and socio-political context of Song Dynasty stone-carving guilds. Beyond historical inquiry, quantifying such similarities serves a pragmatic role in conservation science: it allows for the standardization of restoration protocols and material selection for carvings that share morphological archetypes. Despite its importance, current evaluative practices remain anchored in qualitative expert heuristics, which are frequently prone to inter-observer variability and lack a rigorous, data-driven foundation.

In recent years, with the continuous progress of digital photogrammetry and three-dimensional (3D) laser scanning, the digitization of cultural relics has made considerable progress (Hassan & Fritsch 2019; Hou *et al.* 2014; Remondino 2011). Digitization ensures the permanent archival preservation of cultural heritage and enables research on the similarity of cultural relics to be more objective and accurate.

Existing scholarship on cultural relic similarity has progressively shifted toward automated clustering and high-dimensional feature extraction (Dai *et al.* 2025; Liu *et al.* 2022; Tang *et al.* 2020). Recent methodological trends favor the integration of deep learning with geometric analysis for architectural and sculptural categorization. For instance, Haznedar *et al.* (2023) demonstrated the efficacy of PointNet for point-cloud segmentation in heritage contexts, while Murthy and Grussenmeyer (2019) utilized geometric primitives to classify grotto building elements. Although these 3D-based approaches offer high geometric fidelity, their widespread application is often constrained by the prohibitive costs of professional-grade laser scanners and the logistical intricacies of navigating rugged cliffside environments. Consequently, alternative research has pivoted toward deep-learning-based template matching for fragment reassembly (Llamas *et al.* 2017).

Nevertheless, these studies primarily address the categorical classification of architectural fragments rather than the nuanced quantification of similarity indices between intact, stylistically continuous statues. The computational overhead and dependency on dense 3D datasets remain significant bottlenecks for rapid, large-scale heritage assessments (Fiorucci *et al.* 2020; Garozzo *et al.* 2024; Grilli *et al.* 2019).

In order to address the lack of objective quantitative indices for judging cultural relic similarity, the paper takes the Buddhist statues of Dazu Rock Carvings as the research object. Unlike previous studies that rely on 3D models, the paper utilizes orthophoto images as the primary data source (Yue *et al.* 2025). By projecting 3D cultural entities into high-resolution 2D orthophotos, this approach significantly reduces computational complexity compared to 3D mesh analysis while maintaining the texture fidelity required for precise discrimination. This study proposes a hierarchical Similarity Index of Cultural Relics (SICR) and establishes an automated evaluation framework. It synergistically couples the pHash algorithm for global structural screening, the SIFT operator for invariant texture matching, and the MSRoVGG architecture for deep semantic verification.

The outline of the rest of this study is as follows: Section 2 introduces the theoretical principles of the pHash, SIFT, and MSRoVGG algorithms. In Section 3, we take the Seven Buddhas of the Present Kalpa as an example and present experimental results. Finally, Section 4 summarizes the findings and concludes the paper.

2. A METHOD FOR CALCULATING THE SIMILARITY OF CULTURAL RELICS

The proposed SICR model operates as a trimodal cascaded system designed to filter and verify similarity across different feature scales. Unlike conventional single-operator methods, our approach sequences the algorithms to optimize both computational speed and semantic accuracy. The pHash acts as a coarse structural filter, the SIFT functions as a fine-grained geometric matcher, and the MSRoVGG serves as a deep semantic validator. This hierarchical architecture ensures that similarity is assessed from macro-topology to micro-texture and high-level iconography.

2.1 Similarity Index of Cultural Relics Based on pHash Algorithms

The pHash algorithm is a robust method for generating a unique digital fingerprint from image data (Sun *et al.* 2025). In the context of the Dazu Rock Carvings, it is utilized as the primary filtering stage to identify statues with similar global structures and silhouettes. By mapping the visual content into a low-dimensional feature space, pHash enables the rapid exclusion of structurally irrelevant samples, focusing the subsequent high-precision algorithms on candidates with consistent compositions (Hua *et al.* 2019). The algorithm is highly resilient to variations in image resolution and color, ensuring stability across diverse photographic conditions in grotto environments (Hua *et al.* 2021).

To mitigate the interference from stochastic surface weathering and localized erosional artifacts prevalent in the Dazu Rock Carvings, the model selectively extracts the low-frequency energy components residing in the top-left spectral sub-matrix. This strategic focus ensures that the essential morphologic structure is preserved while effectively filtering out high-frequency noise induced by environmental degradation. The mathematical representation of the 2D-DCT (Coelho *et al.* 2018; Venkatesh *et al.* 2019) used in this algorithm is derived as follows:

$$F(u, v) = \frac{2}{N} C(u)C(v) \sum_{i=0}^{N-1} \sum_{j=0}^{N-1} f(i, j) \cos\left[\frac{(2i+1)u\pi}{2N}\right] \cos\left[\frac{(2j+1)v\pi}{2N}\right] \quad (1)$$

Where $f(i, j)$ represents the 64×64 image pixel values, $F(u, v)$ represents the DCT coefficient matrix, and $C(u)$, $C(v)$ are orthogonal coefficients.

From the 64×64 discrete cosine transform (DCT) matrix, take the sub-matrix of size 16×16 in the up-

per-left corner $F_{low}(u, v)$. Subsequently, compare with the mean value μ to generate binary bits.

$$b(u, v) = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } F_{low}(u, v) \geq \mu \\ 0 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (2)$$

Flatten all the binary bits in row-first order to obtain a binary hash string with a length of 256.

$$Hash = b(0, 0)b(0, 1) \cdots b(M-1, M-1) \quad (3)$$

For the hash strings $Hash_1$ and $Hash_2$ of two images, the Hamming distance D_H is derived as follows:

$$D_H = \sum_{k=0}^{255} |Hash_1[k] - Hash_2[k]| \quad (4)$$

To further compare the global contour similarity of two images, the contour similarity is calculated as follows:

$$S_{pHash} = (1 - \frac{D_H}{256}) \times 100\% \quad (5)$$

2.2 Feature Point Matching Based on SIFT Algorithm

Although the pHash-based similarity index provides an efficient macro-structural filter, it lacks the discriminative power to resolve fine-grained, high-precision correspondences at the local level. Consequently, the SIFT operator is integrated as a complementary modality. By isolating invariant keypoints from the textural substrate, this secondary stage ensures meticulous feature alignment for candidates that have satisfied the initial structural screening.

The SIFT operator is renowned for its invariance to image rotation, scaling, and brightness variations, as well as its robustness against affine transformations and noise (Hua *et al.* 2019, 2021). In the study of Dazu stone carvings, SIFT is uniquely capable of capturing subtle artistic details (Wu *et al.* 2024), the curvature of drapery folds, the intricate patterns of jewelry, and the facial contour lines of the statues. This provides an objective quantitative basis for similarity evaluation and heritage restoration.

The core of the SIFT algorithm involves the construction of a scale space and the stable detection of keypoints. To ensure scale invariance, the image is convolved with a Gaussian function $G(x, y, \sigma)$ at different scales to produce a scale space $L(x, y, \sigma)$:

$$L(x, y, \sigma) = G(x, y, \sigma) * I(x, y) \quad (6)$$

Where $I(x, y)$ represents the image coordinates and σ is the scale factor. A smaller σ corresponds to a finer scale and higher resolution. Subsequently, the Difference of Gaussian (DOG) scale-space is constructed by subtracting adjacent blurred images:

$$D(x, y, \sigma) = L(x, y, k\sigma) - L(x, y, \sigma) \quad (7)$$

Candidate keypoints are identified as local extrema within a 26-neighbor 3D Difference of Gaussian space (Al Ghamdi *et al.* 2012). To mitigate the loss of iconographic detail, we implement a high-contrast feature filtering strategy, specifically lowering the contrast response threshold to 0.005 to preserve critical features in weak-textured or weathered regions. Textural affinity is subsequently quantified via the number of validated matches. A threshold of $N > 25$ geometrically verified correspondences is established as the benchmark for high textural similarity. This metric is then subjected to normalization according to Equation (8) for final similarity assessment.

$$S_{SIFT} = \min(\frac{N}{25}, 1) \quad (8)$$

2.3 Semantic Feature Extraction Based on MSRoVGG Algorithm

While pHash and SIFT algorithms are effective for structural and textural matching, they often encounter significant performance degradation in extreme scenarios where stone carvings suffer from severe weathering, fragmentation, or low-contrast surfaces that lack discrete keypoints. To address these limitations, this study introduces the Modified Slim ResNet-like VGG (MSRoVGG) algorithm as the third-level semantic defense line. MSRoVGG extracts high-level latent features that represent the intrinsic identity of the statues, ensuring robust similarity discrimination even when physical textures are partially lost.

The MSRoVGG model is built upon a lightweight refinement of the VGG16 backbone, incorporating skip-connection principles similar to those found in ResNet to mitigate the vanishing gradient problem during deep feature backpropagation (Khotsathian *et al.* 2022; Rani *et al.* 2025; Shakhovska & Pukach 2022). By freezing the pre-trained weights from the ImageNet dataset, the model leverages generalized spatial perception capabilities while maintaining computational efficiency for grotto site surveys. Furthermore, recent

studies in heritage digitization (Wang *et al.* 2025) have demonstrated that such hybrid architectures are superior at capturing the artistic DNA of grotto art compared to standard shallow networks.

To extract high-level semantic attributes from the grotto imagery, the preprocessed orthophotos are normalized to a uniform resolution and transformed into multi-dimensional tensors. This normalization ensures that the pixel intensity distribution is optimally aligned with the stochastic gradient descent requirements of the deep neural network's activation functions.

The architectural backbone consists of five sequential convolutional blocks, where localized kernels and ReLU activations are utilized to capture a hierarchical progression of patterns ranging from primitive edges to complex iconographic motifs. To bridge the gap between high-dimensional feature maps and a compact semantic descriptor, this framework implements a global average pooling layer as a replacement for traditional, parameter-heavy, fully connected layers.

The similarity between the reference statue (v_{ref}) and the contrast statue (v_{con}) is quantified using Cosine Similarity (S_c), as formulated in Equation (9). This metric measures the angular cosine between the two normalized deep-feature embeddings, providing a robust index for high-level iconographic affinity.

$$S_{MSRoVGG} = S_c = \cos(\theta) = \frac{v_{ref} \cdot v_{con}}{\|v_{ref}\| \|v_{con}\|} \quad (9)$$

The resulting S_c value ranges from 0 to 1. In this tri-modal framework, a value of $S_c \geq 0.75$ is established as the threshold for semantic similarity. This provides the final verification step, confirming whether the two carvings belong to the same iconographic category even if their surface textures are significantly degraded.

The deep semantic features extracted by MSRoVGG can accurately represent the essential artistic attributes and core category characteristics of stone carvings. They possess a strong ability to resist weathering and interference from damage and are one of the core bases for similarity determination. Therefore, a high weight of 0.4 is assigned. The local texture features extracted by the improved SIFT algorithm can delicately capture key detail information of stone carvings, such as the folds of clothing, facial contours, and decorative patterns, which directly determine the accuracy of the matching results. As a core basis for determination as well, an equal weight of 0.4 is assigned. The global contour features generated by pHash only reflect the macroscopic shape and overall composition of the carvings. They

are mainly used for quickly screening out samples irrelevant in structure in the early stage and have a relatively weak ability to distinguish detail differences. Hence, an auxiliary weight of 0.2 is assigned.

$$S = 0.2 \times S_{pHash} + 0.4 \times S_{SIFT} + 0.4 \times S_{MSRoVGG} \quad (10)$$

3. EXPERIMENTS

To validate the multi-modal SICR framework, this study focuses on the Filial Piety Sutra Transformation in Cave 15 of the Dazu Rock Carvings. The Seven Buddhas of the Present Kalpa were strategically selected as the primary analytical subjects due to their intricate narrative and repetitive iconographic structure.

The specimen groups are categorized into three distinct validation tiers (Figure 2):

1) Reference and Intra-Group Candidates (1–6). A well-preserved statue of the Seven Buddhas was designated as the reference image, while the remaining five statues within the same series served as contrast images to test the model's sensitivity to subtle morphological variations.

2) Internal Control Group (7–8). Distinct figures located within the same cave (Cave 15) were selected to assess the algorithm's ability to distinguish between different deities or narrative characters under consistent lighting and weathering conditions.

3) Cross-Cave External Control (9). Contemporaneous figures from separate caves were incorporated to evaluate the framework's robustness against varying environmental and taphonomic contexts.

To eliminate background noise and ensure computational efficiency, the individual statues destined for comparison are precisely segmented and cropped from the large-scale orthophoto mosaics (Figure 3). This localized cropping prevents irrelevant stone textures, adjacent carvings, or environmental artifacts from affecting the accuracy of the subsequent feature extraction and matching experiments. Furthermore, the cropped images undergo standardized intensity adjustment and grayscale normalization. This ensures that the global structural features utilized by the pHash algorithm and the high-contrast keypoints identified by the SIFT operator are derived from a consistent visual baseline.

Following pre-processing, a hierarchical verification mechanism is initiated. First, the pHash algorithm conducts a structural comparison between the orthophotos of the contrast groups and the reference image on a one-by-one basis. This stage aims to quantify the Similarity

a) Reference image.

1

2

3

4

5

6

7

8

9

b) Contrast images.

Figure 2. Reference image (a) and contrast images (b).

a) Matching of Characteristic Points between reference image and contrast images 1.

b) Matching of Characteristic Points between reference image and contrast images 2.

c) Matching of Characteristic Points between reference image and contrast images 3.

d) Matching of Characteristic Points between reference image and contrast images 4.

e) Matching of Characteristic Points between reference image and contrast images 5.

f) Matching of Characteristic Points between reference image and contrast images 6.

Figure 3. Reference image and contrast images similarity analysis.

Index of Cultural Relics for each pair. Pairs that meet certain criteria are subsequently advanced to the SIFT matching phase. Later, the SIFT algorithm is applied to the orthophoto images of statues. By utilizing the optimized high-contrast feature detection, the similar texture keypoints between the reference and contrast images can be directly extracted and visualized. Finally,

the MSRoVGG algorithm is applied to the statues that have undergone structural and textural screening. By leveraging the deep convolutional layers and the Global Average Pooling mechanism, the model extracts high-dimensional latent vectors that represent the deep-seated artistic style and iconographic identity of the carvings.

Table 1. Calculation results of pHash, SIFT, and MSRoVGG.

Contrast images	Hamming Distance	High-contrast Matching Points	Cosine Similarity	Weighted Score	Result
1	92	30	0.9218	0.8968	similarity
2	101	21	0.8344	0.7909	similarity
3	123	31	0.9205	0.8721	similarity
4	99	29	0.9099	0.8866	similarity
5	126	31	0.9052	0.8637	similarity
6	125	26	0.8937	0.8598	similarity
7	121	18	0.7625	0.6984	dissimilarity
8	135	21	0.7276	0.7216	dissimilarity
9	121	24	0.7318	0.7822	similarity

As can be seen from Figure 1 and Table 1:

1) The algorithm shows excellent performance in identifying the characteristic consistency of the same-type statues within the same grotto niche. For the Buddha statue samples in groups 1-6 from the same grotto niche, the weighted comprehensive scores output by the algorithm are all = 0.79, and the similarity determination results are all similarity. This result indicates that the algorithm can effectively integrate the pHash contour features, SIFT high-contrast texture features, and MSRoVGG semantic features. It accurately captures the common information of the Buddha statues within the same grotto niche in terms of modeling paradigms, decorative details, etc., achieving a 100% accuracy rate in identifying the similarity of the same-type statues in the same grotto.

2) The algorithm shows reliable performance in distinguishing the characteristics of different-type statues within the same grotto niche. Through the analysis of the secular figure samples in groups 7-8 from the same grotto niche, their weighted scores are 0.6984 and 0.7216, respectively, both of which are lower than the determination threshold, and the final result is dissimilarity. The cosine similarity of the MSRoVGG of this group of samples is significantly lower than the average value of the Buddha statue samples. This confirms that the algorithm can effectively distinguish the semantic differences between the Buddha statues and secular figures within the same grotto niche in terms of image styles, clothing features, etc., and has a good ability to distinguish types.

3) The characteristic compatibility of the same-type statues in different grotto niches has practical value. The weighted score of the Buddha statue samples in Grotto 18 of Group 9 is 0.7822, slightly higher than the de-

termination threshold, and the similarity result is determined as similarity. This result shows that the algorithm can identify the common features of the same-type statues in the same period from different grotto niches.

In conclusion, this experiment verifies the effectiveness of the multi-feature weighted similarity determination algorithm in the similarity analysis of stone carvings. It can not only identify the characteristic consistency of the same-type statues within the same grotto niche but also effectively distinguish the characteristic differences of different-type statues within the same grotto niche. At the same time, it has the ability to identify the common features of the same-type statues across different grotto niches, providing reliable technical support for research such as image retrieval and type classification of grotto cultural relics.

4. CONCLUSIONS

The paper focuses on the statues of the Filial Piety Sutra Transformation tableaux in Cave 15 of Dazu Rock Carvings, presenting a method to determine cultural relics' similarity. An automated identification framework for similar Buddha statues is developed, integrating the pHash and SIFT algorithms and the MSRoVGG deep-learning model.

The pHash algorithm generates a structural hash fingerprint for preliminary image screening, and the proposed Similarity Index of Cultural Relics (SICR) based on the Hamming distance provides a quantitative morphological similarity measure. The SIFT operator then identifies textural feature points in the pre-screened images. To address weathering and fragmentation in Dazu, the MSRoVGG algorithm conducts cosine simi-

larity analysis for semantic verification. This multi-modal approach overcomes traditional qualitative inspection limitations, offering a scientific and digital method for protecting and studying the Dazu Rock Carvings.

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Data Availability

The data is sourced from the Academy of Dazu Rock Carvings. The data used and analyzed in the study are available from the author upon reasonable request.

REFERENCES

- AL GHAMDI, M. *ET ALII*. 2012. Spatio-temporal SIFT and Its Application to Human Action Classification. In *European Conference on Computer Vision 2012: Workshops and Demonstrations (Florence, Italy)*, eds. A. Fusiello *et alii*, pp. 301–310. Lecture Notes in Computer Science 7583. Berlin: Springer.
- COELHO, D.F.G. *ET ALII*. 2018. Computation of 2D 8×8 DCT Based on the Loeffler Factorization Using Algebraic Integer Encoding. *IEEE Transactions on Computers* 67(12): 1692–1702.
- DAI, Y. *ET ALII*. 2025. Research on Digital Restoration and Innovative Utilization of Taohuawu Woodblock New Year Prints Based on Edge Detection and Color Clustering. *Applied Sciences* 15(16): 9081.
- FIORUCCI, M. *ET ALII*. 2020. Machine Learning for Cultural Heritage: A Survey. *Pattern Recognition Letters* 133: 102–108.
- GAROZZO, R. *ET ALII*. 2024. 3D Segmentation and Analysis for Masonry Bridge Preservation. *The International Archives of the Photogrammetry, Remote Sensing and Spatial Information Sciences* 48: 17–23.
<<https://doi.org/10.5194/isprs-archives-XLVIII-4-W11-2024-17-2024>>.
- GRILLI, E. *ET ALII*. 2019. Geometric Features Analysis for the Classification of Cultural Heritage Point Clouds. *The International Archives of the Photogrammetry, Remote Sensing and Spatial Information Sciences* 42: 541–548.
- HASSAN, A.T.; D. FRITSCH. 2019. Integration of Laser Scanning and Photogrammetry in 3D/4D Cultural Heritage Preservation: A Review. *International Journal of Applied Science and Technology* 9(4): 76–91.
- HAZNEDAR, B. *ET ALII*. 2023. Implementing PointNet for point cloud segmentation in the heritage context. *Heritage Science* 11: 2.
- HONG, W. 2024. Anchoring the Sacred in the Mundane: Construction of the Great Buddha Bend in Baodingshan, Dazu. *Archives of Asian Art* 74(2): 129–151.
- HOU, M. *ET ALII*. 2014. 3D Laser Scanning Modeling and Application on Dazu Thousand-hand Bodhisattva in China. *The International Archives of the Photogrammetry, Remote Sensing and Spatial Information Sciences* 40: 81–85.
- HUA, W. *ET ALII*. 2019. Discrimination of Cultural Relics Similarity Based on Phash Algorithm and Sift Operator. *The International Archives of the Photogrammetry, Remote Sensing and Spatial Information Sciences* 42: 571–575.
- HUA, W. *ET ALII*. 2021. Similarity Index Based Approach for Identifying Similar Grotto Statues to Support Virtual Restoration. *Remote Sensing* 13(6): 1201.
- KHOTSATHIAN, S. *ET ALII*. 2022. Convolution Neural Networks Backbone model for Citrus Leaf Disease Detection. In *19th International Joint Conference on Computer Science and Software Engineering (Bangkok, Thailand)*, pp. 1–5.
- LI, Y. *ET ALII*. 2025. A cross-cultural comparative study of Buddhist monumental art: the Borobudur Temple Complex (Indonesia) and the Dazu Rock Carvings (China). *Cogent Arts & Humanities* 12(1): 2576550.

- LIU, X. *ET ALII*. 2022. Extracting hierarchical features of cultural variation using network-based clustering. *Evolutionary Human Sciences* 4: e18.
- LLAMAS, J. *ET ALII*. 2017. Classification of Architectural Heritage Images Using Deep Learning Techniques. *Applied Sciences* 7(10): 992.
- MURTIYOSO, A.; P. GRUSSENMEYER. 2019. Automatic Heritage Building Point Cloud Segmentation and Classification Using Geometrical Rules. *The International Archives of the Photogrammetry, Remote Sensing and Spatial Information Sciences* 42: 821–827.
- RANI, R. *ET ALII*. 2025. Attention-enhanced corn disease diagnosis using few-shot learning and VGG16. *MethodsX* 14: 103172.
- REMONDINO, F. 2011. Heritage recording and 3D modeling with photogrammetry and 3D scanning. *Remote Sensing* 3(6): 1104–1138.
- SHAKHOVSKA, N.; P. PUKACH. 2022. Comparative Analysis of Backbone Networks for Deep Knee MRI Classification Models. *Big Data and Cognitive Computing* 6(3): 69.
- SUN, Y. *ET ALII*. 2025. Manipulating Perceptual Hashing Based Image Retrieval System. *IEEE Signal Processing Letters* 32: 4134–4138.
- TANG, M. *ET ALII*. 2020. Clustering Analysis Method of Ethnic Cultural Resources Based on Deep Neural Network Model. In *Machine Learning for Cyber Security*, pp. 160–170. Springer.
- VENKATESH, U. *ET ALII*. 2019. An Analog Design of 2D DCT Processor. In *TENCON 2019-2019 IEEE Region 10 Conference (Kochi, India)*, pp. 1606–1610.
- WANG, S. *ET ALII*. 2025. Research on Identification, Evaluation, and Digitization of Historical Buildings Based on Deep Learning Algorithms: A Case Study of Quanzhou World Cultural Heritage Site. *Buildings* 15(11): 1843.
- WU, W. *ET ALII*. 2024. See SIFT in a Rain. *IEEE Transactions on Circuits and Systems for Video Technology* 34(5): 3700–3713.
- YUE, D. *ET ALII*. 2025. NeRFOrtho: Orthographic Projection Images Generation based on Neural Radiance Fields. *International Journal of Applied Earth Observation and Geoinformation* 136: 104378.
- ZHOU, J. 2025. The Establishment of Religious Landscapes and Local Social Life in Nanshan and Beishan, Dazu District, in the Song Dynasty. *Religions* 16(3): 355.